

What can the Galactic bar do to Stellar Streams from Globular Clusters?

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Objectives

- To model the mass loss of all galactic globular clusters
- To understand the effects of how internal dynamics affect stellar streams
- To understand the variety of morphologies of stellar streams in a basic, time static, vanilla, Milky Way potential
- To understand how dynamic perturbations to the Milky Way potential can change the morphologies of streams

Methods

- We built a toy model using a test-particle method in which we simulate the orbits 100,000 star-particles per globular cluster
- Each star particle feels the force of the Milky Way and the host Globular Cluster
- We estimate the initial position of the Globular Clusters by integrating their orbits back in time 5 Gyrs.
- The initial conditions of the Globular Clusters are taken from Baumgardt & Hilker 2018; Baumgardt & Vasiliev 2021; Vasiliev & Baumgardt 2021.
- The Galactic potential models are those of Pouliaxis et al 2017
- The GCs are approximated as static Plummer potentials
- See the article for more details.

SIMULATED TIDAL DEBRIS EMERGING FROM 159 GLOBULAR CLUSTERS

NO BAR

BARRED

Results

- A repository of expected tidal debris from 159 Galactic Globular clusters is publicly available at etidial-project.obspm.fr
- We have shown a variety of morphologies a part from thin stellar streams can be expected from globular clusters
- Our results are consistent with observations for known stellar streams that are already associated to globular clusters
- We have identified a series of streams that are sensitive to the presence of a stellar bar

50 iterations of generating the stellar stream of Palomar 5 superimposed over one another from sampling the errors of the globular cluster's observed kinematics. The tracks of observations are overlain. Short hand citations are shown, which refer to Ibata et al 2021, Price-Whalen et al 2019, Starkman et al 2020. The observations are compiled in the `galstreams` python library (Mateu 2022)

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DATA REPOSITORY

AN ANIMATION

